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Transformational Leadership and Organizational Commitment: Moderating Role of Emotional Intelligence in HEI's in Afghanistan

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Abstract

Academic leaders have a very important role to play in higher educational institutions, and for the development of academic leaders, attention has to be paid to their emotional intelligence to ensure transformational leadership and effective decision-making in their institution. This is because, with the passage of time, the roles of academic leaders have also changed. In the present study, the focus is on the transformational leadership style of academic leaders as it is more prevalent in the higher education institutions in Kabul Afghanistan. This study analyzed the moderating role of Emotional intelligence (EI) of employees on the relationship between transformational leadership (TL) and organizational commitment (OC) in the private higher education institutions in Kabul. The population of the study is the employees of the academics and employees of the 7 private universities in Kabul from that 270 are sample size and the technique used is convenience sampling. The statistical result found that EI acts as a moderator on the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational commitment. This study provides leaders with a new insight to look at their employees' level of commitment to their organization. In addition, this study further helps in exploring the impact of employees' emotional intelligence on the relationship between transformational leadership and different components of organizational commitment. Different aspects of these variables were tested, to provide a wider and more comprehensive understanding of the factors that affect organizational commitment in private higher education institutions in Kabul.

Keywords: Transformational leadership, organizational commitment, Emotional intelligence, HEI in Afghanistan, Organizations

Introduction

Organizations nowadays must make wise decisions to resolve complicated issues because of new difficulties. The top of the organization typically adopts such decisions. At this level, managers and executives have the power to shape the objectives of the organization. Every organization needs strong leaders to increase the dedication, performance, and work happiness of their followers to increase administrative productivity. The objectives of the organization are potentially impacted by the influence and effectiveness of leadership conduct. Increased morale, professional satisfaction, and organizational dedication are some of these objectives or minimize staff transfers, delays, dislocations, and absenteeism.

Over the past 50 years, there has been a lot of global leadership. Given the importance of leadership concerns to an organization's effectiveness, it is not surprising that academic research has been so intense. Corporate representatives struggle to preserve

competitiveness, productivity, and competitive advantage despite strategic and competent leadership. The most common leadership ethos across the previous two periods has been found to be transformative leadership.

According to one definition, transformational leadership is a set of actions that helps followers achieve success that goes above and beyond the norm by altering their attitudes, convictions, and values. The foundations of transformative leadership help followers develop a deep emotional bond with the leader, a shared lofty vision, and the capacity to work together for the benefit of the team, which in turn empowers the followers to make positive changes in themselves. The literature on leadership is clear that transformation leadership is crucial to an organization's effectiveness. A rapidly expanding corpus of research on transformative leadership continues to support the claim that such leaders are beneficial to their teams' ability to produce more advantageous outcomes.

Literature Review

Transformational Leadership

According to Gashema (2021), transformational leadership is an influence process full of values. Leaders adjust their work values to obtain excellent follower performance. Transformational leadership is positively related to the values of corporate social responsibility (CSR) of followers and stakeholders and negatively related to the values of corporate social responsibility of followers and shareholders. A higher-order construct of a person's motivational propensity and persistence toward goals. Positive psychological capital, in turn, has in-role recital and organizational citizenship behavior as consequences. The relationship between empowerment and selected transformational leadership characteristics Intellectually stimulating and individualized consideration positively and significantly contribute to service quality. The power of the leader is a key factor in the leadership model of the organization. Moreover, the influence of leadership characteristics on job performance is directly affected by empowerment. According to Kark (2019), adherents and pioneers work in distinctive areas, and visionary authority is emphatically related to work demeanors, given that the advancement center is adequately tall, and the prevention center is adequately moo. When supporters and pioneers worked in the same location, the individual acknowledgment was emphatically related to work engagement, particularly if the avoidance center or execution objective introduction was tall. It is suggested that effectiveness is enhanced for inter-professional teams when transformational leaders engender dynamics that are characterized by inter-professional motivation and openness to diversity. We suggest that high levels of negative affect enhance the mediating role of interprofessional motivation while low levels of negative affect strengthen the mediating role of openness to diversity.

According to Ismail et al. (2019), managers exercising a transformational leadership style can help to develop a value system in their employees, such as motivation and morals. Transformational leaders have a unique ability to bridge the gap between leaders and followers to develop an understanding of their values.

According to (2017), decades after transformational leadership theory became a major paradigm for leadership scholarships, criticism began to raise serious concerns about their falsifiability, transforming them. It suggests that scholarship theory needs to be abandoned. Transformative leadership is the key to conceptualizing ideal school leadership, but the discourse has not found a way into the field of education. This paper is intended to explain these issues. This essay combines a review of "criticisms of the falsifiability of transformational leadership theories" with a discussion of the usefulness and suitability of the theory. The author suggests that the field of education shouldn't abandon transformational leadership but should instead speak about its shortcomings and look toward the future. The essay examines the present status of the transformational leadership theory in the field of educational administration and offers an explanatory critique.

Transformational Leadership and Organization Commitment

The reason for this thinking was to decide and look at the impact of transformational authority, organizational commitment, and work fulfilment on organizational citizenship behaviour in tall schools in Banter Territory. The test in this study was taken by 220 supervisors of supply chain administration company respondents. This thinks about utilizing the Basic Arbitrary Inspecting procedure to gather information. The strategy used to analyze this information could be a relapse investigation. The results of the investigation and testing show that transformational administration has a positive and noteworthy effect on organizational citizenship behaviour; work fulfilment has a positive critical impact on organizational citizenship behaviour, and organizational commitment has a positive and significant impact on organizational citizenship behaviour. This study demonstrates that transformative leadership, organizational commitment, and "work satisfaction" influence the organization's civic behavior in supply chain management implementation companies.

Concurring to Hadean (2019), it's to know that almost all the suggestions for leadership and organizational commitment for execution, workers state respectful Bandung. The individualized impacts are efficiency, transformative authority, mental stimulation, and individualized thought. The execution of a worker is the work of the quality and amount accomplished through the carrying out of their obligations with transformational authority, commitment, and organization. The inquiry into the strategy used may be a graphic study or a sort of conclusive investigation whose main reason is to describe something that's ordinarily within the form of showcase characteristics or capacities and characterized by the definition of theories. The method of collecting information through a survey.

Agreeing with Rita (2018) on the directing effect of civic behavior on the effect of organizational commitment, transformational authority, and work inspiration on employee execution This thinking points to looking at the relationship between transformational authority, organizational commitment, inspiration, and organizational civic behavior (OCB) and representative efficiency. This study is being carried out in the province of Papua, more specifically in the regional secretariat of Papua. The study was conducted between April and June 2016. This ponder tried the effects of transformational authority, organizational commitment, work inspiration, OCB, and the executive officer of the Papua Common Secretariat. Then the variable pondered was transformational administration, organizational commitment, work motivation, OCB, and official.

In computer programs that examine small structures, the Auxiliary Condition Modeler (SEM) device is frequently utilized. The relationship between organizational commitment, transformational administration, work inspiration, and execution of employees at the Locale Secretariat in Papua Territory does not appear to be significantly impacted by moderating OCB. The effects of organizational commitment, work inspiration, OCB, and performance were all carefully considered. In terms of worker execution, this essay focuses on the direct effects of OCB on organizational commitment, transformational leadership, and work inspiration. This investigation is in the Territory of Papua, more specifically at the Area Secretariat there.

Emotional Intelligence

Mauled et al. did the study (2017). The theory of emotional intelligence (EI) was first presented by Salovey and Mayer in 1990, and Goleman popularized it by publishing his best-selling book *Emotional Intelligence* in 1995. There have been various studies that have used EI measures to measure EI in school leaders even though most of EI tools were initially created in higher education or corporate contexts which I will elaborate on in the part after

this. Since social and emotional abilities are primarily involved in emotional intelligence, I think the term is applicable to all contexts and places. Depending on the requirements of the job or other factors, some skills will be stressed more than others.

According to Singh (2017), I will describe below the three main theories of emotional intelligence, namely, Mayer, Salovey, Goleman, and Barron. The definition of emotional intelligence (EI) is the ability to think about emotions to enhance thinking. It includes the ability to accurately perceive emotions, access and generate feelings to aid thinking, understand feelings and emotional knowledge, and reflexively regulate feelings to promote emotional and intellectual development. They have defined their model in three main categories: evaluation and expression of feelings; emotion regulation; and use of emotions.

Transformational Leadership and Emotional Intelligence

This is a developing debate between supporters and detractors of passionate intelligence and its commitment to authority adequacy in organizational settings. This thinking was done to see how passionate insights relate to the concept of transformational authority. After the organized survey, 20 observational considerations covering all five landmasses were chosen for in-depth investigation. The comes approximately show up that most consider providing exploratory support for the relationship, with the comes almost illustrating that there are variances in recognizing sub-factors of EI and TL that help clarify the EI-TL relationship. At the same time, the remaining ponders are found to be doubtful, not in a general sense denying the relationship but commonly indicating the issue with EI measures and emphasizing the requirement for more substantial and dependable evaluation apparatuses. The display inquiry recommends suggestions for practice and investigation within the human asset advancement field.

According to Potter (2018), the existing investigation has highlighted the requirement for compelling pioneers to reply to the evolving social, financial, and natural imperatives of the development industry. Leadership researchers have considered other divisions and found that persuasive pioneers tend to have a high level of enthusiasm and insight. Concurring to Potter (2018), existing research has highlighted the need for persuasive pioneers to reply to the advancing social, economic, and natural limitations of the development industry. Other divisions have been studied by authority researchers, and they discovered that persuasive pioneers have a high level of enthusiasm. A small investigation has been conducted to examine connections between administrative fashion and enthusiastic insights, particularly regarding construction site supervisors. The investigation group is made up of venture supervisors who are currently working in the development industry in New Zealand and the United Kingdom. The study found that transformational authority styles are common among the venture managers surveyed in this consideration. A noteworthy positive relationship was found between the passionate insights of project supervisors and their probability of receiving a transformational administrative fashion.

A study was conducted by BABA (2021) that scholarly pioneers have a critical part to play in higher instruction education and to create scholarly pioneers their passionate insights must be taken care of to ensure transformational authority and successful decision-making in their organization. There are some issues that all scholarly pioneers confront due to the numerous parts, attitudes, behavior and feelings related to the job/role. Typically, over time, the roles of scholastic pioneers have also changed. This ponders centers on the transformational leadership fashion of scholarly pioneers as they are more predominant within the higher instruction sector. In light of the comes about of observational considers conducted on this subject, this thinks about points to investigate the state of enthusiastic

insights and transformative administration among academic pioneers, and to explore the connections between enthusiastic insights. As a result, it'll be executed within the higher instruction division.

Transformative leadership among scholarly pioneers beneath consider. Ponder the affiliation of different demographic variables of the workforce with respect to passionate insights and their recognition of transformative administration. This research is exploratory and descriptive. The data was collected from full-time faculty working in selected universities in northern India and measured their perceptions of the emotional intelligence and transformational leadership of academic leaders. It turns out that there is a significant and direct correlation between the leader's emotional intelligence and the transformational leadership style perceived by the faculty and staff. The demographic variables (gender and age) were found to significantly influence the variables under study as perceived by the faculty members about their academic leaders. The findings of the study have theoretical implications for conducting further research, which can serve as a reference for service practitioners in designing strategies to ensure the superior performance of academic leaders.

Alcadi (2020) conducted a study titled "Judge the Emotional Intelligence of School Leaders." This study attempts to empirically investigate this phenomenon by examining the EI of Saudi school leaders and the relationship between EI leaders and their work, thereby expanding and advancing existing research in this area. The value of EI was also evident to me during my five-year tenure as a school principal at a previous school that underwent a major transformation. There is research that demonstrates that there are positive correlations between EI, school leadership, and school performance, between transformational leadership and the EI of leaders and school reform. This research focused on the perceptions of Saudi school leaders about the impact of workplace emotional intelligence on their work. I have combined multiple methods to answer my research questions. They also believe that inspirational leadership is key to their work. Moreover, there is a strong positive relationship between the Saudi school leaders' EI and their transformational leadership style.

Non-government organizations are challenged with incapable authority since pioneers have a difficult time overseeing their feelings and the states of mind and behaviors of their followers. In this manner, this thinks about is attempted in arrange to look at the part of leaders' emotions administration in administration adequacy. This think about points to explore how emotional labor procedures, enthusiastic insights and enthusiastic compatibility influence followers' states of mind and behaviors. It moreover looks at the interceding impact of seen transformational administration and the directing impact of seen passionate devotion. The target populace was the pioneers and their coordinated supporters of NGOs in Malaysia and Pakistan. The overview survey strategy was utilized, and information was collected from 374 and 383 sets (pioneer - adherent) individually utilizing cluster inspecting. PLS-SEM was utilized for factual examination. The comes about appeared that leadership's feeling administration played a critical part in shaping the states of mind and behaviors of "followers" that lead to the adequacy of leadership in NGOs.

Enthusiastic work techniques, enthusiastic insights and enthusiastic consonance of officials related to the seen transformative administration as well as the attitudes and behaviors of the adherents. In expansion, the seen transformative leadership in both nations altogether passed on the relationship between pioneers 'emotional work procedures, passionate insights, and enthusiastic arrangement with followers' states of mind and behaviors. In expansion, the seen enthusiastic earnestness moderated the relationship between pioneers 'emotional work techniques and followers' attitudes and behaviors in

both Pakistani and Malaysian NGOs. Several connections were found to be inconsequential in both nations since of relevant variables and specific research settings. Within the consider, which is approximately social contrasts, few connections were altogether different. This thinks about coordinating leaders' feelings with followers' demeanors and behaviors. It moreover gives rules to NGOs with respect to the administration of their leaders' feelings.

In addition, Hunitie (2016) conducted an empirical study on the relationship between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership in Amman public schools in Jordan from the perspective of teachers. The sample includes 250 teachers' selected from 10 public schools in the city. In Hunitie's research (2016), the emotional intelligence of leaders is measured according to the four elements of EI: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management. In addition, transformational leadership is measured using MLQ (Multi-factor Leadership Questionnaire), which was designed by Bass and Avolio (2000). The survey utilized Likert scales, which were outlined to gather information from the teachers who took an interest in the consideration. The analyst found that Passionate Insights is emphatically related to "idealized influence" and altogether impacts "individual consideration," and there's a positive interface between Passionate Insights and "intellectual stimulation." All of these components were measured as a portion of transformational leadership. It is uncovered that passionate insights are emphatically related to transformational administration in a school setting. The limitation of the study is that the data was not triangulated and was only collected from teachers – not principals or their direct managers, who may have a different perspective on leadership. However, it is one of the few studies that looked at emotional intelligence and transformational leadership in the Middle East.

Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Commitment

Concurring to Ahad (2021), enthusiastic insights play an imperative part in motivating individuals to center on their work. A person's state of mind while at work makes an emotional judgment skill coordinated towards the organization's highest efficiency. This circumstance is also a huge issue among the instructors of Malaysian professional schools. The issue is that these instructors are incapable of creating a firm commitment to their organization due to their work demeanor and enthusiastic insights. This quantitative consideration was conducted to investigate the relationship between work demeanors, organizational commitments, and emotional insights among instructors at Malaysian professional schools. The overview was given by 263 respondents, including instructors from professional schools across Malaysia. An investigation with an auxiliary condition modeling (SEM) approach utilizing an Analysis of Minute Structures (AMOS) computer program was actualized. The analysis appears to suggest that there is a significant relationship between a person's work demeanor and their commitment to the organization, as well as a person's enthusiastic insights. Therefore, this consideration can be utilized as a direct partner in overseeing professional colleges, instructors, and organizations legitimately.

Agreeing with Mustafa (2020), this consideration points to approving components related to emotional insights that impact the organizational engagement of professional schoolteachers in Malaysia. To date, the issue of passionate insights is one of the main reasons instructors are committed to their organization, particularly among professional schoolteachers. Ponders have appeared that self-awareness, self-management, social mindfulness, and relationship administration are key components of enthusiastic insights that impact the organizational engagement of professional school instructors in Malaysia. Subsequently, a quantitative study was conducted to confirm the components related to emotional insights. The survey was given to 264 professional college instructors in Malaysia

to arbitrarily select. The information was analyzed utilizing Auxiliary Condition Demonstrating software utilizing the AMOS 21 application. A Corroborative Calculate Investigation was utilized to determine which components were stacked with which things. The investigation comes to show that the variables reflect the fitting fit and meet all the criteria for approval.

This study by Jain et al. (2018) aims to investigate the mediating role of job autonomy in the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational commitment. The mediating role of emotional intelligence will be investigated. To collect data for this study, we used a convenience sampling technique. The study found that talking promotes listening by developing emotional intelligence. Results showed that Emotional Intelligence (EI) acted as the moderator of relationships among the three variables; Turn-ons (TL), Openness to Experience (OC), and Jealousy (JA). The study recommends that leaders that use the TL style should appeal to the emotions of their employees for influencing their OC. This paper extends upon prior research that has identified a relationship between TL and OC; this study proposes and analyzes a comprehensive and theoretically grounded structure of TL, JA, EI and employees' OC, highlighting its theoretical and practical implications.

Agreeing with Akram (2017), the point of the current consideration was to experimentally investigate the intervention impact of organizational commitment within the association between emotional intelligence and work execution within the Pakistani college division. It utilized a sample of around 250 faculty members working at six Islamabad private universities to gather self-reported perceptual-based information assembled through standard questionnaires. The information was analyzed utilizing Basic Condition Modeling (SEM). The study found noteworthy positive impacts of passionate insights on both organization engagement and work execution. It was moreover found that the commitment of the organization contains a critical effect on the work execution of instructors. In expansion, information examination confirmed that organizational commitment plays an intervening part in the relationship between enthusiastic insights and productivity. This think is noteworthy since it is not as it was affirmed it comes from the previous investigation on the subject but moreover contributed to the aggregation of information on the subject.

The comes about can aid professionals and policymakers who apply instructive knowledge to broaden hypothetical points of view on the work of college instructors and formulate arrangements at fitting levels. The conclusion moreover incorporates certain restrictions of the consideration and a few proposals for future analysts. Instruction plays a key part in national improvement, and tall literacy rates can lead to feasible financial improvement, efficiency and financial prosperity for a nation. Be that as it may, it is disheartening that the education rate in Pakistan is only 60%. Instructors are considered the spine of the instruction framework, particularly at the college level, where they are associated with developing understudies. Among a few other factors, counting teachers' destitute execution is considered one of the major reasons for the proficiency rate in Pakistan. The destitute execution among instructors can moreover be credited to moo organizational commitment, tall work disappointment, and the need for capacities to manage the work burnout. Expanding proof proposes that individuals in Pakistan more often than not get into the teaching calling as it were when no other calling has fizzled them. Subsequently, the performance of instructors in common and at the university level in specific should progress to progress the proficiency rate in Pakistan.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

Researchers suggested that transformational leadership is a practical style that benefits leaders in leading higher education changes (Chatterjee & Kulakli, 2015, Drew, 2010).

Hence, researchers recommended the most significant variables that yield a higher prediction of transformational leadership, including leaders' emotional intelligence and self-efficacy (Alston,2009, Ellis,2007, Le et al., 2018; Luthans, 2012, Mesterova et al., 2015; Parrish,2015). Emotional intelligence represents one's capability to monitor the emotion and feelings of one's own and others, thereby distinguishing and managing the thinking and actions of one's own in relationships (Goleman, 2006a; Gutierrez, 2017; Herbert,2011, Schutteetal.,1998). Hence, researchers have identified emotional intelligence as a promising predictor of transformational leadership (Dabke, 2016; Kim & Kim, 2017; Parrish,2015). As explained, leaders without a sufficient level of emotional intelligence would face tremendous challenges while inspiring, challenging, and empowering followers (Caruso&Salovy, 2004). Furthermore, researchers identified that self-efficacy holds extensive influence on organizational outcomes, including transformational leadership behaviors and leadership performance (Bandura, 1997; Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998). Self-efficacy is the belief one has of their capabilities to mobilize the needed motivation, to cognitive resources, initiate courses of action, and encounter situational demands (Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998). Leaders' perception of self-efficacy is a vital factor regarding the motivation of leading and the effectiveness of leadership behaviors (Chan & Drasgow, 2001; McCormick et al., 2002; Nget8al, 2008). Therefore, this correlational study investigated the predictive relationship of the higher education academic administrators' emotional intelligence and self-efficacy to their transformational leadership style.

Fig.1: Theoretical Framework

Source: SI, P et al. (2015).

H1: there is a positive relationship between transformational leadership style and organizational commitment will be stronger when emotional intelligence is high.

Methodology

Since the research aims to find the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational commitment; moderating emotional intelligence in private higher education institutions in Afghanistan, this study uses a quantitative design. This study uses a deductive approach to check the identified factors in the literature in the context of private higher education in Afghanistan. The researcher employed a closed-ended questionnaire divided into two sections. The first section included 6 items to get demographic information about the respondents. The second section included 54 items. To measure the dimensions, a 5-point Likert Scale was applied. The respondents rated their agreement with each item using: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree. Since the study uses a factor analysis approach, according to Bajpai (2011), the sample size should be five times the dimensions included in an EFA study. Based on the literature, 54 dimensions are discussed, so the sample size is 270 which makes up 85% of the 317 targeted audience, and

the population of the study covered two categories of employees; administrative staff and lecturers, who work in private higher education institutions in Kabul City. The sample size was determined using a probabilistic sampling method and the technique used is convenience sampling. To analyze and interpret the primary data, this study used ANOVA test technique.

Results and Discussions

Results

As Table 1 shows, the internal consistency or reliability of the instrument utilized to collect primary data has been tested by the reliability test “Cronbach’s Alpha”. Since the overall level or complete 54 items’ Cronbach’s Alpha value is .0.851 and according to Uma Sekaran words in his book *Research Method for Business*, “The closer Cronbach’s Alpha value is to 1, the higher will be the reliability”. It can be stated that the reliability of the overall complete items level is within the threshold or cut-off as excellent.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Transformational Leadership	.866	15
Organization commitment	.805	15
Emotional Intelligent	.881	24
Total	0.851	54

Source: SPSS output

Normality analysis is all about whether the data collected for the research study is normally distributed or not. If data is normally distributed, then parametric tests are required to be used and if data is not normally distributed, then non-parametric tests should be used. For the sake of checking the normality of the data, each construct has been studied and checked separately. As Table 2 shows that the Skewness values for all variables are within the range (+3, -3) and the Kurtosis value for all the variables is within the range (+10, -10). So, according to (Kline, 2011) the data is normal.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Skewness		Kurtosis	
		Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
TL	270	-.409	.148	-.650	.295
OC	270	.265	.148	-.772	.295
EI	270	-.627	.148	-.032	.295
Valid N	270				

Source: SPSS output

As Table 3 shows, values of VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) of all independent variables are less than 5. It can be stated that the independent variables are not highly correlated with one another or there is low multicollinearity among independent variables.

Table 3: Coefficients

Variables	VIF
1 (Constant)	
TL	1.256

EI	1.256
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a. Dependent Variable: OC

Source: SPSS output

Model Summary

As Table 4 shows, in model 1 the R Square value (.090) shows that the level of the effect by an independent variable is 9% on the dependent variables. In model 2 once the moderating variable “Emotional Intelligence” is added, the level of effect on the independent variable becomes (.283) which is equal to 28.3%. If calculated, the difference is brought to a level of the effect by the moderating variable which is shown in the column R Square Change. In model 3 the interaction effects are also added to independent variables plus the moderating variable and there is an increase in the level of the effect by .329 to model 2 which is also shown in the column R Square Change. The new R Square value became (.329) which is equal to 32.9%. It means the level of the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable will become 32.9% once the moderating variable and interaction effects are added.

In the column “Sig. F Change”, the value of the model interaction effect is less than 0.05 which is significant, and it shows there are some variables that are moderating the relationship between independent variables and the dependent variable.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adj R Square	Std. Error Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.300 ^a	.090	.087	.42511	.090	26.545	1	268	.000
2	.532 ^b	.283	.278	.37802	.193	71.916	1	267	.000
3	.574 ^c	.329	.322	.36640	.046	18.213	1	266	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), TL

b. Predictors: (Constant), TL, EI

c. Predictors: (Constant), TL, EI, TLXEL

Source: SPSS output

The ANOVA test is presented in table 5. As shown in table 5 all three model’s values are .000, which means that emotional intelligence plays moderating role between transformational leadership style and organizational commitment.

Table 5: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.797	1	4.797	26.545	.000 ^b
	Residual	48.432	268	.181		
	Total	53.229	269			
2	Regression	15.074	2	7.537	52.743	.000 ^c
	Residual	38.155	267	.143		
	Total	53.229	269			
3	Regression	17.519	3	5.840	43.500	.000 ^d
	Residual	35.710	266	.134		
	Total	53.229	269			

a. Dependent Variable: OC

b. Predictors: (Constant), TL

c. Predictors: (Constant), TL, EI

d. Predictors: (Constant), TL, EI, TLXEL

Source: SPSS output

H1: the positive relationship between transformational leadership style and organization commitment will be stronger when emotional intelligence is high.

	STD. Beta	S.E	T-Value	Sig.
TL	1.884	0.356	4.413	0.000
EI	1.956	0.343	5.628	0.000
TLXEL	-2.799	0.096	-4.268	0.000

Source: SPSS output

As in the table, since sig. values are .000 we accept the hypothesis. As shown in Table No. 6 the EI categories are divided into two categories low and high and the relationship between transformational leadership style and organizational commitment is stronger when emotional intelligence is high.

Table 6: Statistics

	TL	EI
Valid	275	270
N Missing	12	17
Median	3.8667	3.7917

Source: SPSS output

Discussions

Organizations nowadays face new difficulties that call for them to make important decisions to deal with complex problems. At the best firms, choices are frequently made available. Destinations are under the control of pioneers and organizational leaders. According to one description, the idea of transformative authority has an impact on followers by enlarging and elevating their goals and providing them the confidence to carry out tasks beyond those specified in the explicit or specific trade understanding. Organizational commitment is seen as an important factor in figuring out how people behave at work.

The purpose of this study is to analyze how employees' emotional intelligence (EI) affects the relationship between organizational commitment (OC) and transformational leadership (TL) in Kabul's private higher education institutions. Employees from Kabul's 7 private universities and academic institutions make up the study's population. The sample size is 270, and convenience sampling is the sampling method. According to the statistical findings, EI moderates the association between organizational commitment and transformative leadership. At the same time, we discovered that the results are consistent with earlier research. (Samir et al, 1993, Petrides and Farnham, 2006, Copper and Wible, 2006 and Pile, 2008).

Moreover, Farahani (2011) found that there is a substantial and positive correlation between organizational commitment and transformational leadership, with a regression value of 0.046. This sum demonstrates a favorable and strong correlation. Additionally, it is discovered that emotional intelligence mediates the association between transformational leadership and organizational commitment, which, from a statistical perspective, has a quantity of 0.026 and is positive and significant.

The research also offers recommendations for firms on how transformational leadership creates an environment that fosters employee commitment to and level of job satisfaction while moderating emotional intelligence. Employee commitment and loyalty to

firms are closely related to employee satisfaction levels. The business needs to retain those personnel for the long term and invest heavily in their training and growth if they want to remain satisfied representatives who see themselves as its most valuable resources.

Recommendations

- Some of Kabul's private institutions include lecturers who are older than 60, according to research. After retiring from public universities, they move on to teach at private institutions. Instructors lack or have less stamina at this age to impart knowledge. It is advised against naming experienced instructors for instructional purposes.
- In the private universities of Kabul, the chancellors and principles governed with an autocratic leadership style. No one is channeling for them, and they make all decisions.
- The democratic culture in educational institutions is essential for fulfilling universities' objectives. Additionally, university administrators should value and respect teachers.
- To ensure that this appropriate style fits the circumstance, it is also recommended that thought be given to the growth of leadership in the organizational environment. Additionally, rather than controlling their teams' job activities, transformational leaders should put more of their attention on guiding them.
- Finally, to minimize the friction between manager and leader, supportive management is necessary to balance leadership with management. Top management needs to understand how crucial leadership is to retaining current personnel and getting the job done via them.

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